

Knowledge and Understanding of Malay Symbols in Indonesia: Survey Method

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 08 , 2024</p> <p>Accepted: March 10 , 2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Knowledge, Understanding, Malay Symbols, Tradition</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15000763</p>	<p><i>This article aimed to find out quality of knowledge and understanding of Malay symbols. Data of this study are important for educators when they educate their students Malay symbols, especially in University of Riau. A survey involving 870 samples was carried out. The data were presented in descriptive statistics and inferential statistics focusing on respondent characteristics and Malay symbols on games, food and drink, clothing, and ornaments. The research findings revealed that the mean score of knowledge and understanding of the game aspect was 4.34 and the understanding of the meaning of symbols was 4.49. Both of the scores belonged to the very high category. In the aspect of food and drink, the mean of knowledge of the symbols was 3.81 and the understanding of the meaning of symbols was 3.87. Both scores belonged to the high category. In the clothing aspect, the mean of knowledge of Malay symbols was 4.07 and the understanding of the meaning of the symbol was 4.04 which both scores belonged to the very high category. Dealing with the aspect of ornament, the mean of knowledge of Malay symbols was 3.96 and the understanding of the meaning of the symbols was 3.87. Both of the scores belonged to the high category. In general, the mean of knowledge of the Malays symbols was 4.045 (very high) and that of understanding the symbols was 4.065 (very high). The category of knowledge of Malay symbols by University of Riau students belonged to the very high category. In addition, the findings revealed that there was no significant difference between recognizing Malay symbols and understanding of Malay symbols in terms of gender, education level, and religion. However, there was a significant difference in recognizing Malay symbols and understanding of the symbols of the Malay tradition in terms of ethnics.</i></p>

Introduction

Symbols, in Malay culture, has been acknowledged as a reference to Malay identity so far (Khalis & Mustaffa, 2017; Tong & Robertson, 2008; Jory, 2007; Smolicz, 1981). These symbols can be depicted in terms of several aspects, such as food and drink, games, clothing, and ornaments. It is important to know these symbols as an attempt to preserve the cultural values contained therein. As human beings, people should keep and preserve their culture in order that it survives and grows. Saving culture such as tradition needs hard work. A lot of information is available in electronic media or applications. However, it does not touch human beings (Nagata, 1974).

Technology keeps developing. Therefore, it is necessary for human beings to have awareness to study cultural values so that they have knowledge and understanding of the existing symbols of Malay culture (Hussein, 1966). In other words, a person should not only recognize the cultural values but also know functions and ways to use the values. When talking about clothes such as *Baju Kurung Cekak Musang*, a person should know not only its shape but also its function as well as the ways to wear it. Such knowledge is important to maintain the spirit and preserve the existence of these symbols (Carr & Landa, 1983). Therefore, it is important that any person in Riau, let alone a person studying Malay culture has good knowledge and understanding of the symbols.

Nowadays, there are various kinds of expression and cultural patterns in accordance with their advantages and disadvantages (Kitayama & Markus, 2000; Larkey 1996). Baidhawiy and Jinan (2003) assured that there are several factors that shape cultural diversity, namely: internal power authority as a political expression and religious understanding, either in terms of *fiqh* sect (religious sect), ethnic and racial characteristics of Muslims. These characteristics have influenced all aspects of the symbols of Malay culture (Ely & Thomas, 2001; Welsch, 1999) such as art, music, calligraphy, ornament and architecture, and clothes as well as jewellery.

This article discusses the quality of knowledge and understanding of Malay symbols in terms of the aspect of game, food and drink, clothing and ornament. Data obtained from this study could be important for

academicians and member of society in Riau in general. Kinds of Malay food consisted of *ketupat sayur*, *ayam goreng kunyit*, *ayam pedas*, *daging masak ketumbar*, *ikan sembilang gulai tempoyak*, *ikan sembilang pedas*, *jenggan*, *gulai nenas*, and *ikan kurau masin* (Raji et al, 2017; Lipoeto et al 2001; Adnan, 2017; Bujang, 1994). The Malay also have a wide variety of cakes (Borthwick, 2010; Coppock, 1973), such as *kue talam manis*, *kue talam belauk*, *putu piring*, *bahulu/bolu kamboja*, *anta kesuma*, *kole-kole*, *putu mayang*, *alwa nikmat*, *aman sari jepang*, *bahulu/bolu berendam*, *apam*, *lempeng petanak*, *pengat pisang*, *mahkota pecah intan*, *pengat labu*, *serikaya kerwang*, *lopes/lupis pulut*, *kue jongkong*, *bingka ubi*, *ongol-ongol*, *puteri dua sebilik*, *roti belauk*, *sambal belacan*, *sambal bilis*, *otak-otak*, and so forth. In addition, kinds of drink of the Malay consisted of *laksamana mengamuk* and *air dohot kesemak*.

Traditional games originating from Riau, in general, can be classified into two groups, namely: indoor games and outdoor games (Welki & Zlatoper, 1999; Lever, 1976). Indoor games consist of *congklak*, *gasing* (spinning top), *statak* (*hopsotch*), *petak umpet* (hide-and-peek), *benteng* (fortifications) and *biji karet* (rubber seeds). Meanwhile, outdoor games consist of *lulu cina buta* (the blind person), *bakiak* (wooden sandals with a rubber toe strap), *engrang*, *layang-layang* (kites), *tarik tambang* (tug-of-war), *kelereng* (marbles) and *ligu* (Ningsih, Firzal, & Aldy, 2020). The games can also be classified based on place and time the game played and the tools used (Rashid, Saman, & Syahrani, 2016).

In terms of clothes, there are various kinds of clothes that the Malay have (Insani, 2018; Aris, 2015; Hassan Zaman, & Santosa, 2015). Based on the classification of the users, daily clothing can be divided into children's clothes, adult clothes, and elder persons or middle-aged clothes. Early aged children's clothes are called *baju monyet* (monkey clothes). After a boy grows up, he wears *Baju Teluk Belanga* or *Baju Cekak Musang*. A boy sometimes also wears half or below the knee pants, a cap, and a head cover made of rectangular cloth. He also wears sarong when studying and reciting the Quran and worshipping. Meanwhile, underage girls wear *baju kurung* that matches the floral patterned fabric or the same colour with the fabric (Na'am et al, 2019).

An adult man commonly wears *Baju Kurung Cekak Musang* which is worn with a sarong. He also wears a cap or headband. Meanwhile, an adult lady commonly wears *Baju Kurung Laboh*, *Baju Kebaya Pendek*, and *Baju Kurung Tulang Belut*. This clothes are combined with batik sarong and head cover. The sarong functions as a scarf or a hood. Ladies who work in a field, for examples, in a rice field usually wear a head scarf or unbleached calico cloth called *Tengkuluk* (Na'am et al., 2019).

There are various kinds of clothes worn by elder lady or middle-aged lady, such as *Baju Kurung Teluk Belanga* (that is also called *Baju Kurung Tulang Belut*), *Kebaya Laboh*, and *Baju Kebaya Pendek* commonly worn when she goes to work at a field. She also wears a veil to cover his head. The veil is triangular in shape so that it resembles a hijab. Meanwhile, elderly and middle-aged gentleman wear *Baju Kurung Teluk Belanga* or *Baju Kurung Cekak Musang*. The clothes are made of cotton or *lejo*. The clothes are a bit loose so they are comfortable to wear. The clothes are also worn in a formal events (Na'am et al, 2019).

In addition to games, there are various kinds of food, drink, and ornaments used by the Malay. The ornaments are commonly designed with certain motifs, such as plants, animal, natural objects, and combination motifs. The plant motif generally includes vegetables, such as: ferns, bamboo shoots, and trailing plants with crimson flowers. The animal motif comprises of ants, chickens or ducks, fish, bees, birds, grasshoppers, and fruit-eating flying fox. The elements used can be partial or whole. The types of the motifs consist of *semut beriring*, *itik sekawan*, *lebah bergantung*, *siku keluang*, and *merpati sekawan*. Ornaments with natural objects includes clouds, moon, stars, sun, waves, *awan larat*, *awan jawa*, *awan semayang*, and *awan boyan*. Meanwhile, the combination motif includes a combination of plant, animals, and natural objects motifs. Such combination can be found in calligraphy (Pane & Fachrudin, 2020; Hashim et al, 2017; Ammarell & Tsing, 2015; Utaberta & Rasdi, 2014; Ammarell, 1988).

Research problem

1. What is the level of knowledge and understanding of Malay symbols?
2. Is there a significant difference level of knowledge and understanding of Malay symbols in terms of gender?
3. Is there a significant difference level of knowledge and understanding of Malay symbols in terms of academic year level?
4. Is there a significant difference level of knowledge and understanding of Malay symbols in terms of ethnics?
5. Is there a significant difference level of knowledge and understanding of Malay symbols in terms of religion?

Correlation between Demographics and knowledge and understanding of Malay Symbols

A point of view that someone has on Malay symbols culture in terms of food and drink, games, clothing, and ornaments cannot be separated from his/her personal condition. His/her psychological condition has the potential to influence him/her. It is necessary to concern with the quality of the demographic aspects of the respondents. This aspects relate to gender, semester, age, ethnic of origin, and religion. Martin et al (2002); Bussey & Bandura (1999); Campbell et al (2002) assured that gender plays an important role in achievement. Thus, data on knowledge and understanding of the aspects of food and drink, games, clothing and ornaments are strongly influenced by gender. Gender enables a person to explore information. Such characteristic is

inseparable from the number of semester that a student has taken. The higher the semester a student has taken, the higher or the better the experience or knowledge he has. Ardi et al (2012) carrying out an observation on 270 students deduced that the duration of study of a student has a correlation with his/her knowledge. To ensure this quality, a person must have a good plan in his/her study (Sikora, 2013; Erlauer, 2009; & Sousa, 1998).

In the growth and development theory, the age range of 15 to 45 is categorized as a productive period (Sukmaningrum, 2017). During the period, a person has an ability to learn, deepen his/her knowledge and understand an object or problem. Students as respondents of this research are in the range 17-30 years old. During the age period, a person is able to develop his/her cognitive abilities. According to Miller (2009), at the period, a person can optimize his/her reasoning and thinking. It means that students can do their best to gain knowledge and understand information.

An ethnic requires its individuals to keep learning (Chakraborty & Ghosh, 2013). The existence of ethnicity is a determinant of character in exploring knowledge and understanding the meaning of Malay symbols. During learning, there will be social interaction to achieve learning goals. Even though the things learned are not the same as that of their own ethnic groups, what they study or learn does not reduce the learning objectives. It shows that the average knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols in terms of the ethnic origin is in the high category.

Religion also plays an important role in motivating someone to learn. It is related to the knowledge and understanding of Malay symbols. Niculescu & Norel (2013) assured that religion triggers a person to have good knowledge and understanding. Studying the cultural symbols supports a person to interact with his religious experience. Itulua-Abumere (2013) said that religion is able to stimulate and increase an involvement of a person in certain activities. In this perspective, exploring the knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols is considered as an attempt to implement religious insights. In addition, Malay symbols are able to clarify the actions that must be taken, both in the context of religion and social life. It is proven that every religion in the data above showed a high standard. The data emphasized that demographic elements need to be considered in observing the quality of knowledge and understanding of an object or information.

Method

A method used in this study was a survey method. The population of this study was University of Riau students. The sampling technique used was the simple random sampling. The basic description is based on the instrument used for the data collection, i.e., a questionnaire. The instrument related to the aspects food and drink, games, clothing, and Malay ornament. There were 10 questions in each aspect. Observations were made with a Likert scale consisting of five answer or response options. The instrument or questionnaire was distributed to 870 students of University of Riau. Since this research was carried out during the Covid-19 pandemic, the number of the sample was the students who responded the questionnaire. The data were collected by using a google form. This strategy was taken due to its effectiveness to collect data.

There were two types of data collected. They were primary data and secondary data. The primary data were obtained from the questionnaire filled in by the students. Meanwhile, the secondary data were additional data and supporting primary data. The secondary data were obtained from a library, such as literature, journals, articles, newspapers, and the internet. The technique used for data collection was a questionnaire. The Likert scale was used in this study. The Likert scale contained statements that shows the attitude of the respondent's knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols. The alternative answers provided in the questionnaire were as follows: (1) not qualified, (2) less qualified, (3) fairly qualified, (4) qualified, and (5) very qualified. The score ranges were 0,1, 2, 3, and 4.

The data analysis of this study were carried out by finding out the mean and standard deviation and observing each questionnaire item that was filled in by the respondents. The steps taken were: collecting the instrument that was filled in, tabulating respondents' answers for analysis, analysing each item containing the respondent's responses, describing data or information by correlating and comparing to other research findings and theories to answer the formulation research questions and objectives of this study, and drawing final research conclusions based on the formulation of the problem and research objectives. The data were analysed by using descriptive statistics. For inferential analysis, an independent t test and one way ANOVA were taken. The decision regarding the category of quality and understanding of Malay symbols was taken based on the assessment criteria as presented in table 1.

Table 1. Interval and Assessment Criteria

No.	Scale		Category
	Positive	Negative	
1	4.01—5.00	2.01—1.00	Very high
2	3.01—4.00	3.01—2.00	High
3	2.01—3.00	4.01—3.00	Low

4	1.00—2.00	5.00—4.00	Very low
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Results

Games

The findings of the descriptive analysis of respondents based on the aspect of games include the mean and standard deviation (SD) as shown in a table below.

Table 2. Interpretation of research data i terms of the aspect of games

No.	Indicator	Knowledge			Understanding		
		Mean	SD	Category	Mean	SD	Category
1	<i>Gasing</i>	4.52	0.759	Very high	4.49	0.812	Very high
2	<i>Bakiak</i>	4.43	0.825	Very high	4.44	0.815	Very high
3	<i>Congkak</i>	4.60	0.713	Very high	4.55	0.745	Very high
4	<i>Enggrang</i>	4.41	0.810	Very high	4.42	0.849	Very high
5	<i>Layang-Layang</i>	4.56	0.776	Very high	4.52	0.812	Very high
6	<i>Tarik Tambang</i>	4.58	0.743	Very high	4.57	0.745	Very high
7	<i>Petak Umpet</i>	4.49	0.832	Very high	4.45	0.849	Very high
8	<i>Benteng</i>	4.14	0.996	Very high	4.16	1.034	Very high
9	<i>Ligu</i>	3.56	1.136	High	3.69	1.213	High
10	<i>Statak</i>	4.08	1.073	Very high	4.13	1.047	Very high
	<i>Mean</i>	4.34	0.866	Very high	4.49	0.812	Very high

There were 10 kinds of games as basis for data collection and analysis in Table 2. They were *Gasing*, *Bakiak*, *Congklak*, *Enggrang*, *Layang-Layang*, *Tarik Tambang*, *Petak Umpet*, *Benteng*, *Ligu* and *Statak*. Quantitatively, the mean of knowledge of Malay symbols was 4.34 and understanding of the meaning of the symbols was 4.49. Both the mean scores belonged to the *very high* category. The respondents or the students had very good knowledge and understanding of the Malay games. Based on this data, it is believed that in addition to knowing the types of and variety of games, they were also able to understand the games, how to make the equipment of the games, how to play the games, and what the goals of the games are.

Food and Drinks

The findings of the descriptive analysis of respondents based on food and drink included the mean and standard deviation as presented in the following table.

Table 3. Interpretation of Research Data in Terms of the Aspect of Food and Drink

No.	Indicator	Knowledge			Understanding		
		Mean	SD	Category	Mean	SD	Category
1	<i>Ikan Sembilang Pedas</i>	3.61	1.001	High	3.77	1.180	High
2	<i>Kue Asidah</i>	3.62	1.036	High	3.78	1.138	High
3	<i>Bolu Kemojo</i>	4.44	0.858	Very high	4.34	0.948	Very high
4	<i>Kue Talam Manis</i>	4.43	0.822	Very high	4.35	0.933	Very high
5	<i>Puteri Dua Sebilik</i>	3.5	1.088	High	3.66	1.178	High
6	<i>Putu Mayang</i>	4.13	0.971	Very high	4.13	1.027	Very high
7	<i>Mahkota Pecah Intan</i>	3.49	1.071	High	3.58	1.187	High
8	<i>Kue Jongkong</i>	3.39	1.118	High	3.53	1.209	High

No.	Indicator	Knowledge			Understanding		
		Mean	SD	Category	Mean	SD	Category
9	<i>Laksamana Mengamuk</i>	4.18	0.994	Very high	4.13	1.053	Very high
10	<i>Air Dohot Kesemak</i>	3.33	1.150	High	3.47	1.217	High
	<i>Mean</i>	3.81	1.011	High	3.87	1.107	High

There were 10 kinds of the food and drink as the basis for data collection and analysis. They were *Ikan Sembilang Pedas*, *Kue Asidah*, *Bolu Kemojo*, *Kue Talam Manis*, *Puteri Dua Sebilik*, *Putu Mayang*, *Mahkota Pecah Intan*, *Kue Jongkong*, *Laksamana Mengamuk*, and *Air Dohot Kesemak*. Data in the table showed that the quality of knowledge of food and drink was at the same standard. The mean of knowledge was 3.81 and the understanding of symbols was 3.87. Both of the mean scores belonged to the *high* category. It means that there was no difference in knowledge of the Malay symbols. Knowledge of the food and drink functions as the basis for understanding of types of food and drink.

Clothing

The findings of the descriptive analysis of respondents in Terms of the Aspect of Clothing include the mean and standard deviation as presented in the following table.

Table 4. Interpretation of Research Data in Terms of Clothing

No.	Indicator	Knowledge			Understanding		
		Mean	SD	Category	Mean	SD	Category
1	<i>Baju Monyet</i>	3.55	1.137	High	3.73	1.150	High
2	<i>Baju Teluk Belanga</i>	4.14	1.004	Very high	4.05	1.067	Very high
3	<i>Baju Cekak Musang</i>	4.00	1.077	Very high	4.00	1.076	Very high
4	<i>Baju Kurung Cekak Musang</i>	4.14	1.006	Very high	4.06	1.093	Very high
5	<i>Kopiah</i>	4.65	0.692	Very high	4.51	0.814	Very high
6	<i>Tanjak</i>	4.48	0.858	Very high	4.42	0.904	Very high
7	<i>Kurung Laboh</i>	4.14	0.993	Very high	4.02	1.087	Very high
8	<i>Baju Kurung Tulang Belut</i>	3.91	1.062	High	3.86	1.151	High
9	<i>Baju Kebaya Pendek</i>	3.85	1.047	High	3.85	1.073	High
10	<i>Tengkuluk</i>	3.88	1.071	High	3.90	1.142	High
	<i>Mean</i>	4.07	0.995	Very high	4.04	1.056	Very high

There were 10 kinds of clothes as the basis for data collection and analysis of the aspect of clothing. They were *Baju Monyet*, *Baju Teluk Belanga*, *Baju Cekak Musang*, *Baju Kurung Cekak Musang*, *Kopiah*, *Tanjak*, *Kurung Laboh*, *Baju Kurung Tulang Belut*, *Baju Kebaya Pendek* and *Tengkuluk*. The mean of knowledge of the Malay symbols was 4.07 and the mean of understanding of the meaning of symbols was 4.04. Both of the means belonged to the *very high* category. The means also pointed out that there was no difference in knowledge of the Malay symbols. In addition, they means that the students had very good knowledge of the Malay symbols in terms of the Malay clothing.

Ornaments

The findings of the descriptive analysis of respondents in terms of ornaments was presented in the table below.

Table 5. Interpretation of the Data in Terms of Ornaments

No.	Indicator	Knowledge			Understanding		
		Mean	SD	Category	Mean	SD	Category
1	<i>Kaluk Pakis</i>	3.88	1.055	High	3.86	1.137	High

No.	Indicator	Knowledge			Understanding		
		Mean	SD	Category	Mean	SD	Category
2	<i>Pucuk Rebung</i>	4.27	0.929	Very high	4.14	1.011	Very high
3	<i>Selembayung</i>	3.98	1.074	High	3.91	1.103	High
4	<i>Sayap Layang-Layang</i>	3.94	1.043	High	3.86	1.145	High
5	<i>Semut Beriring</i>	3.98	1.018	High	3.93	1.118	High
6	<i>Itik Sekawan</i>	4.09	1.002	Very high	3.98	1.116	High
7	<i>Lebah Bergantung</i>	4.04	1.025	Very high	3.90	1.131	High
8	<i>Siku Keluang</i>	3.85	1.099	High	3.75	1.197	High
9	<i>Awan Larat</i>	3.77	1.118	High	3.68	1.210	High
10	<i>Awan Semayang</i>	3.81	1.129	High	3.70	1.226	High
	<i>Mean</i>	3.96	1.049	High	3.87	1.139	High

In table 5, it can be seen that there were 10 kinds of the ornaments used as the basis for data collection and analysis. They were *Kaluk Pakis*, *Pucuk Rebung*, *Selembayung*, *Sayap Layang-Layang*, *Semut Beriring*, *Itik Sekawan*, *Lebah Bergantung*, *Siku Keluang*, *Awan Larat* and *Awan Semayang*. The mean of knowledge of the Malay symbols was 3.96 and the mean of understanding of the meaning of the Malay symbols was 3.87. Both of the means belonged to the *high* category. The data also showed that the knowledge of the Malay symbols that the students had was in line with their understanding of the Malay symbols in terms of the ornaments. In addition, the findings revealed that there was no difference in terms of knowledge of the Malay symbols. In other words, the students had very good knowledge.

Differences in knowledge and understanding of the Malay Symbols in Terms of Gender

Before a t test analysis was conducted, skewness and kurtosis had been conducted on knowledge and understanding of traditional Malay symbols to find out the normality test in terms of gender. The skewness value for the male group was -0.684, while the kurtosis scores was 0.460. The skewness value for the female group was -0.785, while the kurtosis scores was 0.165. The scores showed that knowledge and understanding of the symbols of the Malay tradition in terms of gender were normally distributed. Thus, to find out differences in knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols, an independent t-tests was taken. The findings of the analysis can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6. Differences in knowledge and understanding of Malay Symbols in Terms of Gender

Group	N	Mean	Standard deviation	t	df	Sig	Category
Male	226	3.56	0.70	0.480	868	0.631	High
Female	644	3.54	0.65				High

Table 6 showed that there was no significant difference between knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols in terms of gender with $t = 0.480$ and $\text{sig} = 0.631$ ($p > 0.05$). It pointed out the null hypothesis (H_0) that there is no significant difference in knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols in terms of gender was accepted. It can be concluded that students' knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols between female and male students was not different.

Differences in knowledge and understanding of the Malay Symbols in Terms of Academic Year Level

Before the Anova analysis was carried out, skewness and kurtosis had been taken on knowledge and understanding the Malay symbols to find out the normality in terms of academic year level. The skewness value for all groups ranged from -0.893 to -0.629, while the kurtosis scores ranged from -0.536 to 0.420. It pointed out that knowledge and understanding the Malay symbols in terms of academic year level was normally distributed. Moreover, the outputs also pointed out there was no significant variance-covariance differences among the dependent variables for each group, $F = 4.183$, $p > 0.001$, which could be interpreted as variance-covariance for the knowledge and understanding the Malay symbols was homogeneous across academic year level. Thus, to find out differences in knowledge and understanding the Malay symbols in terms of academic year level, an Anova test was taken. The findings showed that there was no significant differences in knowledge and

understanding the Malay symbols in terms of on academic year level in which $F = 2.793$ and $p = 0.097$ (as shown in Table 7).

Table 7. ANOVA of Knowledge and Understanding the Malay Symbols in Terms of Academic Year Level

Variables	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Knowledge and Understanding the Malay Symbols	2.793	3	.931	2.116	.097

This pointed out that the null hypothesis (H_0) that there is no significant difference in knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols in terms of academic year level was accepted. It can be concluded that students' knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols in terms of academic year was not different. Table 8 presented the mean and standard deviation of students' knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols in terms of academic year.

Table 8. Mean and standard deviation of students' Knowledge and Understanding of the Malay Symbols in Terms of Academic Year

Dependent Variable	Knowledge and Understanding of the Malay Symbols	Category
Year 1	3.42 ± 0.74	High
Year 2	3.50 ± 0.68	High
Year 3	3.57 ± 0.70	High
Year 4	3.57 ± 0.66	High

Table 8 showed that that students of Year 3 ($M = 3.57$ and $SD = 0.70$) and year 4 ($M = 3.57$ and $SD = 0.66$) had higher knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols than other groups. Moreover, students of Year 1 had the lowest mean scores ($M = 3.42$ and $SD = 0.74$).

Differences in Knowledge and Understanding of the Malay Symbols in Terms of Ethnic

To find out the normality based on ethnic, skewness and kurtosis were carried out on knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols. The skewness scores for all groups ranged from -0.843 to -0.422 , while the kurtosis scores ranged from -0.772 to 0.405 . This showed that knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols in terms of ethnics was normally distributed. Moreover, the findings revealed that there was no significant variance-covariance differences among the dependent variables for each group in which $F = 7.606$, $p > 0.001$. So, it could be interpreted as variance-covariance for the knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols is homogeneous inter-ethnic. Thus, an Anova test was taken to find out differences in knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols in terms of ethnics. The findings showed significant differences in knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols in terms of ethnics, in which $F = 3.031$ and $p = 0.017$ (Table 9).

Table 9. ANOVA of Knowledge and Understanding of the Malay Symbols in Terms of Ethnic

Variables	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols	5.306	4	1.327	3.031	.017

This showed that the null hypothesis (H_0) that there is no significant difference in knowledge and understanding of the Malay tradition symbols in terms of ethnic was rejected. It can be concluded that students' knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols in terms of ethnics among the groups was different. Table 10 presented the mean and standard deviation of students' knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols in terms of ethnics.

Table 10. Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Knowledge and Understanding of Malay Symbols

Dependent Variable	knowledge and understanding of Malay Symbols	Category
Malay	3.56 ± 0.64	High
Jawa	3.56 ± 0.64	High

Batak	3.38 ± 0.70	High
Minang	3.57 ± 0.82	High
Lain-lain	3.35 ± 0.80	High

Table 10 showed that students of Minang ethnics ($M = 3.56$ and $SD = 0.82$) had higher knowledge and understanding of Malay symbols than other groups. Meanwhile, other ethnics got the lowest mean scores of knowledge and understanding of Malay symbols, ($M = 3.35$ and $SD = 0.80$). In addition, mean of Malay ethnic, Java ethnic and Batak ethnic were ($M = 3.56$ and $SD = 0.64$; $M = 3.56$ and $SD = 0.64$; $M = 3.38$ and $SD = 0.70$) respectively.

Differences in Knowledge and Understanding of Malay Symbols in Terms of Religion

A skewness and kurtosis were carried out on knowledge and understanding of Malay symbols to find out the normality in terms of religion. The skewness value for all groups ranged from -0.767 to -0.320 , while the kurtosis scores ranged from -0.428 to 0.350 . This showed that that knowledge and understanding of Malay symbols in terms of religion was normally distributed. The findings also revealed that there was no significant variance-covariance differences among the dependent variables for each group, $F = 2.982$, $p > 0.001$, which could be interpreted as variance-covariance for the knowledge and understanding of Malay symbols is homogeneous inter religion. Thus, an Anova test was taken to find out differences in knowledge and understanding of Malay symbols in terms of religion. The findings revealed that there was significant differences in knowledge and understanding of Malay symbols in terms of religion, where $F = 1.005$ and $p = 0.321$ (Table 6).

Table 11. ANOVA of Knowledge and Understanding of Malay Symbols in Terms of Religion

Variables	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Knowledge and Understanding of Malay symbols	1.005	2	.502	1.138	.321

This indicated the null hypothesis (H_0) that there is no significant difference in knowledge and understanding of the symbols of the Malay tradition based on religion was accepted. It can be concluded that students' knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols among the groups was not different. Table 12 presented the mean and standard deviation of students' knowledge and understanding of the symbols of the Malay tradition in terms of religion.

Table 12. Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Knowledge and Understanding of Malay symbols

Dependent Variable	Knowledge and Understanding of Malay symbols	Category
Islam	3.55 ± 0.65	Tinggi
Catholic	3.39 ± 0.76	Tinggi
Protestant	3.47 ± 0.80	Tinggi

Table 12 showed that respondents of whose religion is Islam ($M = 3.55$ and $SD = 0.65$) had higher knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols than that of other groups. Meanwhile, the lowest mean scores of knowledge and understanding of symbols of the Malay tradition belonged to respondents whose religion is Catholic, where $M = 3.39$ and $SD = 0.76$). In addition, the mean scores of knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols by respondents whose religion is Protestant was $M = 3.47$ and $SD = 0.80$.

Discussion

The respondents or students had very good knowledge and understanding of the Malay games. For example, *layang-layang* (play kite game). Kites are not played all the time. There are played at certain times. This context required the players to have good knowledge and understanding of the game. A kite is a symbol of harmony and generally played during the rice harvest season (Roy, Kuan, & Tenenbaum, 2016). In line with its development, this game became a national game and was contested. Supriyono (2018) the traditional game of kite is timeless. This game is very popular for children, teenagers, and adults. Although the game can be found in many places, the young generation should understand the nature of the game.

It is very possible that the traditional games are played at certain events. The games not only entertain people attending the events but also walk hand in hand with objectives of the events. Synergy between the events and the traditional games is able to promotes the events. For this reason, students must have knowledge and understanding of the various games available so that they can prepare the various needs if required. Such

preparation is aimed to save the traditional games in the modern era. If the traditional games are not preserved, it is very possible that the games are left and replaced by modern games.

It is important to know and understand the traditional games of the Malay people so that the games save. Yunus (1982) assured that traditional games as one of the elements of national culture need to be saved and preserved. An attempt that can be done is to study, document, and play the games. Nowadays, games can be created in an application (Atan, Indra, & Febtriko, 2020; Agustina & Wahyudi, 2015). However, players cannot feel and achieve the philosophical values of the games if they are played through an application only. Bastian and Novitasari (2019) reassured that the Malay traditional games must be introduced and promoted. If introduction and promotion are not held, the traditional games will be marginalized by global technology development that keeps presenting various modern electronic games.

In a daily life of the Malay people, food served has its own objectives. Some food and drink is served at certain events only. *Kue Asidah* (Asidah cake), for example, is a typical food for kings (royal blood people). The cake is used to be served at festivals, engagement, religious holidays, feast, and wedding ceremony. It means that Asidah cake is a symbol of Malay tradition because it is served at certain moments or for certain and special people. Other food or drink also enrich the colour or uniqueness of the Malay community. Currently, some of these food and drink can be found in restaurants.

Although the food and drink can be found in restaurants nowadays, Fitaliya et al (2019) assured that these traditional food and drink must be passed down from one generation to the next generation so that people of future generation know and understand them. Currently, there are so many kinds of food and drink that are sold in the Malay community. If the traditional food and drink is not passed down from generation to generation, these food and drink can be left behind. Furthermore, Fitaliya et al (2019) reassured that traditional food and drink is one of the cultural traditions that must be preserved. Therefore, people are required to maintain their own local wisdom. Thus, traditional food and drink as cultural symbols can be preserved and developed and seen as very valuable cultural tradition.

In Riau, the Malay clothing has become part of official uniform in several agencies and institutions, both public and private. However, the traditional costumes are worn in certain occasions, such as: customary meeting and wedding ceremony. In the context of traditional clothing, of course, knowing the traditional cloth is not enough. People must understand how to wear it. Insani (2020) assured that anyone needs to know the appropriateness in wearing clothes. If he/she does not wear a costume appropriately, the objective of wearing the costume will not be achieved. That is why students need to have a deep understanding of the meaning contained in Malay clothes. The way to wear the Malay costumes shall follow certain provisions.

Students, as young generation must understand the Malay tradition, especially the traditional clothes. Meanwhile, loose and long *baju kurung* has been very commonly worn by people in Riau. Based on Insani's record (2020), it was Tun Hasan who changed it to be loose and long. This history is also recorded in the book entitled "Pakaian Patut Melayu" (Proper Malay Clothes), written by Dato 'Haji Muhammad Said Haji Sulaiman. Nowadays, information about the use and types of Malay traditional clothes can also be obtained in various applications. Technology enables all information to be can be obtained from media such as handphones (Agustina & Wahyudi, 2015). A student, of course, can get information from not only the media but also empirical experience. In other words, a direct learning process runs so that he/she gets his/her own experience regarding knowledge and understanding of the Malay clothing. Traditional clothes must be passed from generation to generation because they bring the identity of greatness and pride (Sandra et al, 2019).

Dealing with Malay ornaments, they can be found in traditional Malay houses, monuments, buildings, or traditional and government buildings. A personal property, such as house may have ornaments too. Each ornament has its own meaning according to its shape and name. The use of this ornament is a characteristic or symbol of Malay identity. Each part has characteristics, including colour of an ornament. In addition to beautify a building, Azmi (2012) and Sunaryo (2009) assured that the use of ornaments has specific purposes.

An ornament usually has symbolic values that relate to the way of life or philosophy of life. It also relates to an object where the ornament is applied to. It means that an ornament plays an important role for its users. An ornament is used to both express feeling and convey the cultural values contained therein. The *Kaluk Pakis* ornament, for example, symbolizes humbleness and friendliness. It is expected that a person uses the ornament will be a humble and friendly person. Another example is *Pucuk Rebung* (bamboo shoot). The ornament symbolizes fertility and happiness. So, it is expected that a person using the ornament will be fertile and happy. It is important for a person to understand the philosophy in order that he/she puts an ornament properly.

A motif of an ornament, for the Malay people, functions as not only a decoration but also a symbol that has meaning and philosophy regarding the noble values of the Malay culture (Juliana & Zaharani, 2019). A person should have knowledge and understanding of the motif. Therefore, he/she can preserve the Malay ornaments and pass them from generation to generation. If they are not preserved, the ornament motifs functioning as traditional symbols of the Malay people will disappear. Juliana and Zaharani (2019) and Juliana et al (2018) noted that a few craftsmen made mistakes in visualizing Malay motif on ornaments. Consequently, the

philosophical value of the motif of the ornament reduced or even lost. If no attempt is taken to improve such condition, philosophical values as a feature of the local wisdom of the Malay community will fade away.

Martin & Ruble (2010) noted that men and women have different abilities in building knowledge and understanding an issue. Martin et al. (2002); Bussey & Bandura (1999); Campbell et al. (2002) assured that each gender has a motivational quality in learning and understanding. In line with Liben & Bigler (2002); Martin & Ruble (2004) stated that gender plays an important role in showing an ability to get knowledge or understanding. This explanation reminds us that gender plays an important role in showing its achievements. Data in Table 2 showed that there was no significant difference between knowledge and understanding of the symbols of the Malay tradition. Both groups; men and women had the same standards.

In the Malay tradition, both men and women have different roles. However, both men and women must understand Malay symbols and play their role as the successor and heir of generations. Therefore, both men and women have the same responsibility to save the symbols. Nowadays, not only men but also women require to have various kinds of information and skills (Prager, 2020; Sultana, 2010). In another context, men and women can share ideas on the Malay symbols. Both men and women are encouraged to have adequate knowledge and understanding. Men and women can work together hand in hand (OECD, 2017). That there is no significant difference in the knowledge and understanding between men and women is an advantage (Rehman & Roomi, 2012) which can be a means of informing the Malay symbols.

The semester level that the respondents were in was a pointer in understanding the Malay symbols. The duration of time spent by the respondents for their learning activities also plays an important role to gain knowledge and understanding. Within a certain period, a person is very likely to have the skills to manage information or his empirical experience (Rech et al, 2007) so that he/she has good knowledge and understanding of an object or an issue. Ardi et al (2012) carried out a survey on 270 students. The findings of the survey revealed that duration of study has a correlation with their knowledge and understanding. Various possibilities can occur when knowledge and understanding is viewed from the aspect of the duration of study. The quality of a person's knowledge and understanding can get better or worse with various risks (Eze & Misava, 2017). To ensure the quality, a person must have good planning in his study (Sikora, 2013; Erlauer, 2009; Sousa, 1998; & Lengnick-Hall, 1995).

The findings of this research also revealed that there was no significant relationship between each semester in knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols. It means that the level of the semester passed by the respondents played no role in building a person's knowledge and understanding. This happens because sociologically the atmosphere when respondent studied integrated into the Malay tradition. Therefore, they have knowledge and understanding of these symbols (Greider & Garkovich, 1994). In a social behaviour approach point of view, a person can understand many things cognitively (Stajkovic & Luthans, 1998). There was a response so that before studying in a university, they already had knowledge and understanding of issues related to the Malay symbols from various aspects. In other words, the information obtained when they studied in a university functions to confirm their perceptions.

Ethnicity inherent from birth is a favour. An ethnic commonly has its own culture. The culture becomes the character of the ethnic. However, when students deriving from various ethnicities study in the same place, the ethnic does not become a barrier in exploring knowledge and understanding. In general, each ethnic requires its individuals to continue learning (Chakraborty & Ghosh, 2013). The existence of the ethnic influences the character in exploring knowledge and understanding. During learning, there will be social support to achieve learning goals. Mustafa et al (2018); Zulhafizh et al (2013); Haveman and Smeeding (2006) assured that it is important to understand that this method is aimed to encourage each person or individual to have positive learning motivation. Even though what a person studies is not the same with what his/her ethnic group studies, what he/she studies does not decrease the learning objectives. This shows that the mean of knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols in terms of the ethnic origin belonged to the *high* category.

The means of knowledge and understanding of the Malay symbols from all religion groups belonged to the *high* category. It means that there was no difference in the quality of knowledge and understanding of the meaning among respondent whose religion is Islam, Christianity and Protestant. In this context, religion plays an important role in motivating its followers to learn everything needed, including knowledge and understanding of Malay symbols. Niculescu & Norel (2013) assured that religion triggers a person to have good knowledge and understanding. Studying the cultural symbols motivates a person to interact with his religious experience. Itulua-Abumere (2013) stated that religion can stimulate and increase involvement of its followers. In this perspective, exploring the knowledge and understanding of the field of Malay symbols is in line with religion point of view. The Malay symbols are able to clarify an action that must be taken, both in religion and social context. In addition, the data pointed out that each religion showed a high standard.

Conclusion

In terms of the characteristics of the respondents, the research findings revealed that there was no significant difference in knowledge and understanding of Malay symbols. The mean was 3.48. The game aspect belonged

to the same standard. The mean of knowledge and understanding was 4.34 and the understanding of the meaning of the symbol was 4.49. Both of the mean scores belonged to a very high category. The mean of the aspect of food and drink belonged the same standard. The mean of knowledge was 3.81 and the mean of understanding of the meaning of the symbol was 3.87. Both of the mean scores belonged to the high category. The clothing aspect belonged to the same standard. The mean of knowledge was 4.07 and the mean of understanding of the meaning of Malay symbols was 4.04. Both the mean scores belonged to the very high category. The ornament aspect also belonged to the same standard. The mean score of knowledge was 3.96 and the mean of understanding of the meaning of the Malay symbols was 3.87, Both the mean score belonged to the *high* category. Overall, the mean of knowledge was 4.045 that belonged to the very high category and the mean of understanding of symbols was 4.065 that belonged the very high) category. The quality of knowledge of the meaning of Malay cultural symbols among students at the University of Riau belonged to the very high category. This finding means that there was no difference between knowledge of the meaning of the symbols of Malay tradition among students of the University of Riau.

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References

- Adnan, F. (2017). *Menjelajah kuliner tradisional Riau*. Jakarta: Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan Badan Pengembangan dan Pembinaan Bahasa.
- Agustina, C., & Wahyudi, T. (2015). Aplikasi game pendidikan berbasis android untuk memperkenalkan pakaian adat Indonesia. *Indonesian Journal on Software Engineering (IJSE)*, 1(1), 1-8.
- Ammarell, G. (1988). Sky calendars of the Indo-Malay archipelago: Regional diversity/local knowledge. *JSTOR*, (45), 85-104.
- Ammarell, G., & Tsing, A. L. (2015). Cultural production of skylore in Indonesia. *Handbook of Archaeoastronomy and Ethnoastronomy, New-York, Springer Science*, 2207-2214.
- Ardi, R., Hidayatno, A., & Zagloel, T. Y. M. (2012). Investigating relationships among quality dimensions in higher education. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 20(4), 408-428.
- Aris, A. (2015). Refleksi Islam dalam pakaian tradisional Melayu: Baju kurung. *Conference: ICOMHAC 2015*, at Langkawi, Kedah, 1-10.
- Atan, A., Indra, Z., & Febtriko, A. (2020). Perancangan game berbasis android untuk memperkenalkan adat Melayu Riau. *Rabit: Jurnal Teknologi dan Sistem Informasi Univrab*, 5(1), 54-66.
- Azmi. (2008). Memahami karya seni rupa kontemporer melalui karya semiotika. *Jurnal Seni Rupa FBS UNIMED*, 5 (2) 2-3.
- Baidhawiy, Z., & Jinan, M. (2003). *Agama dan pluralitas budaya lokal*. Surakarta: PSB-PS UMS.
- Bastian, A., & Novitasari, Y. (2019). Permainan tradisional berbasis budaya Melayu dalam pengembangan karakter anak. *Affāhunā: Journal of Islamic Early Childhood Education*, 2(2), 53-56.
- Borthwick, K. (2010). The Community Café Project: Sharing tea, cake and online teaching resources. *ALISS Quarterly*, 6(1), 23-25.
- Bujang, I. (1994). *Makanan: wujud variasi dan fungsinya serta cara penyajiannya pada orang Melayu, Jambi*. Jakarta: Direktorat Jenderal Kebudayaan.
- Bussey, K., & Bandura, A. (1999). Social cognitive theory of gender development and differentiation. *Psychological review*, 106(4), 676-713.
- Campbell, A., Shirley, L., & Caygill, L. (2002). Sex-typed preferences in three domains: do two-year-olds need cognitive variables?. *British Journal of Psychology*, 93(2), 203-217.
- Carr, J. L., & Landa, J. T. (1983). The economics of symbols, clan names, and religion. *The Journal of Legal Studies*, 12(1), 135-156.
- Chakraborty, S., & Ghosh, B. N. (2013). Ethnicity: A continuum on education. *Online Submission*, 3(2), 128-147.
- Coppock, J. B. M. (1973). Bread, buns, biscuits and cakes. *Royal Society of Health Journal*, 93(5), 237-240.
- Ely, R. J., & Thomas, D. A. (2001). Cultural diversity at work: The effects of diversity perspectives on work group processes and outcomes. *Administrative science quarterly*, 46(2), 229-273.
- Erlauer, L. (2009). The brain-compatible classroom: Using what we know about learning to improve teaching. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 1(2009) 37-41.
- Eze, C., & Misava, E. (2017). Lecture duration: a risk factor for quality teaching and learning in higher education. *Integrity Journal of Education and Training*, 1, 1-5.
- Fitaliya, F., Simanjuntak, H., & Syahrani, A. (2019). Medan makna makanan tradisional dalam bahasa Melayu dialek Sukadana. *Jurnal Pendidikan dan Pembelajaran Khatulistiwa*, 8(11), 1-9.

- Greider, T., & Garkovich, L. (1994). Landscapes: The social construction of nature and the environment. *Rural sociology*, 59(1), 1-24.
- Hashim, M. H., Ahmad, A. M. A. Z., Latif, M. P. A., & Yunus, M. Y. M. (2017). Visual communication of the traditional house in Negeri Sembilan. *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, 5(2), 112-123.
- Hassan, H., Zaman, B. A., & Santosa, I. (2015). Tolerance of Islam: A study on fashion among modern and professional Malay women in Malaysia. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanity*, 5(5), 454-460.
- Haveman, R., & Smeeding, T. (2006). The role of higher education in social mobility. *The Future of children*, 16(2), 125-150.
- Hussein, I. (1966). The study of traditional Malay literature. *Journal of the Malaysian Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society*, 39(2 (210)), 1-22.
- Insani, S. N. (2020). Baju kurung sebagai pakaian adat suku Melayu di Malaysia. *Foreign Case Study*. Yogyakarta: Sekolah Tinggi Pariwisata Ambarukmo Yogyakarta
- Itulua-Abumere, F. (2013). The significance of religious education in local primary schools (specific reference to christianity). *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 6(6), 69-94.
- Jory, P. (2007). From Melayu Patani to Thai Muslim: The spectre of ethnic identity in southern Thailand. *South East Asia Research*, 15(2), 255-279.
- Juliana, J., & Zaharani, H. (2019). Revitalisasi filosofi ornamen bermotif Melayu pada Desain corak anyaman gedebong pisang: Kajian kearifan lokal budaya Melayu. *Jurnal Ilmiah Lingua Idea*, 10(1), 12-28.
- Juliana, J., Fatimah, F., & Apriliyanti, A. (2018). Empowering and fostering creative industries entrepreneurs based on local wisdom of Malay Deli. *KARSA: Journal of Social and Islamic Culture*, 26(2), 215-250.
- Khalis, F. M., & Mustaffa, N. (2017). Cultural inspirations towards Malaysian animation character design. *Jurnal Komunikasi: Malaysian Journal of Communication*, 33(1).
- Kitayama, S., & Markus, H. R. (2000). The pursuit of happiness and the realization of sympathy: Cultural patterns of self, social relations, and well-being. *Culture and subjective well-being*, 1, 113-161.
- Larkey, L. K. (1996). Toward a theory of communicative interactions in culturally diverse workgroups. *Academy of Management Review*, 21(2), 463-491.
- Lengnick-Hall, M. L. (1995). The owner's manual for the brain: everyday applications from mind-brain research. *Personnel Psychology*, 48(3), 683.
- Lever, J. (1976). Sex differences in the games children play. *Social problems*, 23(4), 478-487.
- Liben, L. S., Bigler, R. S., Ruble, D. N., Martin, C. L., & Powlisha, K. K. (2002). The developmental course of gender differentiation: Conceptualizing, measuring, and evaluating constructs and pathways. *Monographs of the society for research in child development*, i-183.
- Lipoeto, N. I., Agus, Z., Oenzil, F., Masrul, M., Wattanapenpaiboon, N., & Wahlqvist, M. L. (2001). Contemporary Minangkabau food culture in West Sumatra, Indonesia. *Asia Pacific journal of clinical nutrition*, 10(1), 10-16.
- Martin, C. L., & Ruble, D. (2004). Children's Search for gender cues: Cognitive perspectives on gender development. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 13(2), 67-70.
- Martin, C. L., & Ruble, D. N. (2010). Patterns of gender development. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 61, 353-381.
- Martin, C. L., Ruble, D. N., & Szkrybalo, J. (2002). Cognitive theories of early gender development. *Psychological Bulletin*, 128(6), 903-933.
- Miller, L. M. S. (2009). Age differences in the effects of domain knowledge on reading efficiency. *Psychology and Aging*, 24(1), 63-74.
- Mustafa, M. N., Hermandra, Zulhafizh, & Hermita, N. (2018). the significance of language motivations learning: correlation analysis. *Advanced Science Letters*, 24(11), 8080-8083.
- Na'am, M. F., Wahyuningsih, S. E., Setyowati, E., Prasetyaningtyas, W., Kamis, A., & Susanto, M. R. (2019). Riau Malay traditional clothes: Functional, symbolic, aesthetic, and cluster state studies. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineerin*, 8(1C2), 652-655.
- Nagata, J. A. (1974). What is a Malay? Situational selection of ethnic identity in a plural society. *American ethnologist*, 1(2), 331-350.
- Niculescu, R. M., & Norel, M. (2013). Religious education an important dimension of human's education. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 93, 338-342.
- Ningsih, E. F., Firzal, Y., & Aldy, P. (2020). Penerapan prinsip desain Daniel Libeskind pada fasilitas permainan tradisional Melayu Riau di Pekanbaru. *ARTEKS: Jurnal Teknik Arsitektur*, 5(2), 219-228.
- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). (2017). *Gender balance guideactions for UAE organisations*. Paris: OECD Publishing.
- Pane, I. F., & Fachrudin, H. T. (2020). Changes of form of Malay traditional houses in Medan and surroundings. *Britain International of Humanities and Social Sciences (BIOHS) Journal*, 2(2), 495-502.

- Prager, L. (2020). Emirati women leaders in the cultural sector: from “state feminism” to empowerment?. *Hawwa*, 18(1), 51-74.
- Raji, M. N. A., Ab Karim, S., Ishak, F. A. C., & Arshad, M. M. (2017). Past and present practices of the Malay food heritage and culture in Malaysia. *Journal of Ethnic Foods*, 4(4), 221-231.
- Rasyid, S., Saman, S., & Syahrani, A. (2016). Klasifikasi kosa kata permainan rakyat Melayu Sambas: Pendekatan etnolinguistik. *Jurnal Bahastra*, 35(2), 75-101.
- Rech, J., Decker, B., Ras, E., Jedlitschka, A., & Feldmann, R. L. (2007). The quality of knowledge: knowledge patterns and knowledge refactorings. *International Journal of Knowledge Management (IJKM)*, 3(3), 74-103.
- Rehman, S., & Roomi, M. A. (2012). Gender and work-life balance: A phenomenological study of women entrepreneurs in Pakistan. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 19 (2), 209 - 228
- Roy, J., Kuan, G., & Tenenbaum, G. (2016). Sport psychology service delivery in Malaysia: an introduction to common cultural norms and experiences. *J. Phys. Act. Sports Exerc.*, 1, 22-29.
- Salthouse, T. A., & Miles, J. D. (2002). Aging and time-sharing aspects of executive control. *Memory & Cognition*, 30(4), 572-582.
- Sandra, E., Malik, A., & Elfitra, L. (2019). Makna simbolik pakaian upacara adat Melayu Kota Tanjungpinang Kepulauan Riau <http://repository.umrah.ac.id/3308/>
- Schaie, K. W. (1993). The Seattle longitudinal studies of adult intelligence. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 2(6), 171-175.
- Sikora, D. (2013). What Great Teachers do (or Should do): Innovative Brain-Based Instructional Strategies. *Techniques*, 88(7), 38.
- Smolicz, J. (1981). Core values and cultural identity. *Ethnic and racial studies*, 4(1), 75-90.
- Sousa, D. (1998). How the brain learns: more new insights for educators. *A presentation on August 18, 1998*, in Port Washington, WI. 31.
- Stajkovic, A. D., & Luthans, F. (1998). Social cognitive theory and self-efficacy: Going beyond traditional motivational and behavioral approaches. *Organizational dynamics*, 26(4), 62-75.
- Sukmaningrum, A. (2017). Memanfaatkan usia produktif dengan usaha kreatif industri pembuatan kaos pada remaja di Gresik. *Paradigma*, 5(3), 1-6.
- Sultana, A. (2010). Patriarchy and women s subordination: A theoretical analysis. *Arts Faculty Journal*, 1-18.
- Sunaryo. A. (2009). *Ornamen nusantara*. Semarang: Dahara Prize
- Supriyono, A. (2018). *Serunya permainan tradisional anak zaman dulu*. Jakarta: Badan Pengembangan dan Pembinaan Bahasa, Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan.
- Tong, M. C. A., & Robertson, K. (2008). Political and cultural representation in Malaysian websites. *International Journal of Design*, 2(2).
- Utaberta, U., & Rasdi, M. T. H. M. (2014). Evaluating the discontinued traditions of Malay wood carvings in Malaysia: A failure to develop the discourse on modern and post modern ornamentation in architectural works. *American Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, 7(2), 241-254.
- Welki, A. M., & Zlatoper, T. J. (1999). US professional football game-day attendance. *Atlantic Economic Journal*, 27(3), 285-298.
- Welsch, W. (1999). Transculturality: The puzzling form of cultures today. *Spaces of culture: City, nation, world*, 13(7), 194-213.
- Yunus, A. (1982). *Permainan rakyat Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta*. Jakarta: Departemen Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan, Proyek Inventarisasi dan Dokumentasi Kebudayaan Daerah.
- Zulhafizh, Atmazaki, & Syahrul R. (2013). Kontribusi sikap dan motivasi belajar siswa terhadap hasil belajar bahasa Indonesia. *Jurnal Bahasa, Sastra dan Pembelajaran*, 1(2), 13-28.
- Zulhafizh. (2020). Orientation on implementation of learning curriculum at senior high school: teacher's perspective. *Jurnal Pajar (Pendidikan dan Pengajaran)*, 4(2), 303-315.
- Zulhafizh., & Permatasari, S. (2020). Developing quality of learning in the pandemic covid-19 through creative and critical thinking attitudes. *Jurnal Pajar (Pendidikan dan Pengajaran)*, 4(5), 937-949.

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